

THE STORY "YODGOR" IS AN EXAMPLE OF TRUE HUMAN QUALITIES

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Abstract. This article provides detailed information, conclusions, and opinions about Gafur Ghulam's short story "Yodgor". It highlights the story's inspiring messages of nationalism, humanity, and the importance of learning. The narrative is a powerful reminder of the strength of the human spirit and the importance of standing up for what is right. It encourages readers to think critically about the world around them and to take action to make a positive difference. The story is a testament to the power of literature to move and inspire people.

Key words: Mehrikhan, Jora, Yodgor, nationality, knowledge, humanity.

Gafur Ghulam's story "Yodgor" was written in 1936 and tells about the fates of Mehrikhan, Jora and Saodat. Throughout the work, we can come across many scenes that represent our nationality. For example, father Mehrikhan, who refuses the monument due to the honor of his family, or Jora, who writes a letter to Saodat and requests a yarmulke. In her letter, Jora explains the reason for the cap request as follows: "Here everyone wears their national clothes, and I wanted to wear our national yarmulke for the holidays." The work also reflects humanity, learning and love for the country. The play actually begins with Jora's meeting with Mehrikhan. According to him, Jora behaves like a sincere, simple person and gratefully tries to help Mehrikhan and even goes to the registry office with him, saying that he divorced Mehrikhan. After that, all events will begin. Mehrikhan

completes the plan to get rid of the child at the registry office, and Jora's adventures with Yodgor begin.

Reading this work, we can truly appreciate the power of a mother's love. When Jora brings Yodgor to his mother and she initially believes he is one of her daughter's children. However, after Jora reveals the truth, the old woman is understandably upset. Jora's description of his feelings towards his mother further emphasizes the strength of a mother's love: "Oh, mother who took care of me with your heart, oh, mother who gave me all you have, oh, don't close your eyes for my education mother Oh, mother who is blessed with the darkness of dark nights, oh, mother who is blessed with bright days in your future! Who in the world is more kind than mother? I still couldn't write a poem equal to the songs you sang above the crib. I have not yet felt as much sorrow as you did for the little fever that broke out of me." Through these lines, we can witness the unconditional love a mother has for her child, even when they are apart. We can also see the pain a mother feels when her child is sick or in danger. Although Mehrikhon's actions may initially seem cruel, it is important to remember that she was desperate and was trying to protect her family's honor. Her regret, the stain on her child, and the seven years of longing all lead to her illness. This work serves as a reminder of the immense love a mother has for her child, and the lengths she will go to protect them.

During the play, we can witness not only mother's love, but also love for the motherland. At the age of 22, Jora goes to Ashgabat for 2 years of military service and meets many people during his service. His desire to serve his country, to be a useful person for his children and his country in the future, prompts him to study in Leningrad for 4 years after 2 years of military service, where military doctors are trained. He faces many difficulties, such as his aunt's decision not to marry his daughter Saodat, his brothers turning their backs on him, as well as the fact that he does not know the Russian language when he joins the military service. But he perseveres and overcomes all these obstacles. His mother rubs the

letter sent by Jora on her eyes, praises it to her neighbors, that my son is proud to be the leader of the government, her brother writes a letter to Jora again, that everyone is fine, and try to give money, so as a help to Jora. The fact that his sending money and that Yodgor is doing well is proof that Jora has successfully overcome all difficulties. This story instills in the heart of the person who reads it a great confidence that bright destinations will come after any difficult days, and encourages them to strive for their goals. Despite the hardships he faced during military service and his studies, Jora eventually became a military doctor, proving that with hard work and dedication, anything is possible.

Of course, it is wrong to say that the work is only about maternal love or love for the country. The work also serves to encourage young people to acquire knowledge. Because after Saodat got engaged to Jora, she entered pedagogy. Jora, of course, supports her act and writes the following thoughts in a letter: "I was very delighted to hear that you entered the university. Every girl who wants to be successful in the future must study." Through this work, Ghafur Ghulam encourages all young men and women to learn and reach the heights of enlightenment. A knowledgeable, highly spiritual woman raises a knowledgeable child. A knowledgeable child can certainly create a bright future that will benefit the country. A woman may not become a scientist, but she can give birth to future scientists. Gafur Ghulam calls not only the girls of our country, but also women from all over the world to get an education through the work "Yodgor".

After reading the story, conflicting thoughts, ideas, and emotions may arise in the mind of the reader. At the end of the story, Jora's confrontation with Mehrikhan, Mehrikhan's regret, and Yadgor's visit to the Mehrikhan family are all signs that true human qualities always triumph over evil. When Jora first found Yadgor, he was still a newborn baby. He lovingly raised the child as if he were the apple of his eye. Despite the difficulties of the past years, Mehri's cruel rejection of the child allowed Yodgor to live with the Mehrikhans. This act of kindness by Jora is an example of true humanity. Furthermore, Gafur Ghulam's

unique writing style effectively conveys the difficulties of life, and his narrative techniques, characteristic of Eastern literature, are creative and convenient to use. It is no surprise that the compositional construction of the story, the way the plot developed, the use of the art of modeling, and the appeal to the epistolary genre were all clearly visible in the work and gave it a special appeal.

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